

RESIN FLOW AND COMPACTION IN FILAMENT WOUND CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

A process model for filament winding and consolidation of composite cylinders was developed and experimentally validated. The model relates the processing conditions (applied temperature, fiber tension, and processing speed) to temperature, degree of cure, void content, fiber volume fraction, and stresses and strains within the composite cylinder. A **unique** feature in this model is the affect of these processing conditions on the void content and distribution in the cylinder. Critical to the void characterization is the pressure gradient in the composite during processing. As such, two resin flow/pressure gradient submodels (sequential compaction and sponge compaction) are evaluated and compared. For experimental validation of the winding model, several 0.51 m (20 in) diameter, thick graphite/epoxy cylinders were wound. Tow tension, layup, and resin viscosity characteristics were varied. In addition to experimental validation of temperature and strain predictions, experimental results are compared with model predictions of void content and fiber volume fraction for these winding conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The filament winding process has emerged as a primary method for manufacturing composite structures at low cost. This automated process offers a high speed, precise method for laydown of continuous reinforcements to form closed shape composite structures. To ensure final parts which meet strength and geometry requirements, the relationship between processing conditions and final part characteristics must be clearly understood. Composite cylinders may be manufactured from continuous fibers impregnated with a thermosetting or thermoplastic polymer matrix. The focus of this paper will be on "wet" filament winding of thermosetting matrix cylinders.

During wet filament winding, continuous fiber tows are passed through a resin bath and wound onto a rotating mandrel (Figure 1). Tension F_o is applied to the tows as they are placed on the mandrel by a moving crosshead. The relationship between the crosshead speed V and the mandrel angular velocity ω determines the fiber orientation or winding angle ϕ_o . Once winding is complete, the cylinder is cured at an elevated temperature and the mandrel is removed. The final cylinder may also undergo a post cure cycle. Thus, the process conditions which can be selected and controlled independently are: (1) winding speed and hold time between layers; (2) initial fiber tension for each layer during winding; and (3) external temperatures, heating rates and pressures during the winding, cure and post cure stages.

For filament winding of thermosetting matrix composite cylinders, process models have been developed to study consolidation and fiber motion during winding, changes in fiber tension during winding, composite temperature and subsequent cure, changes in void size during winding and the final mechanical strength of the cylinder [1-3]. Each of these models has particular strengths for various applications. The research by Springer and coworkers [1] provides a complete model for the entire filament winding process and has been experimentally validated for prepreg thermosetting matrix cylinders. The models posed by Gutowski [2] and Agah-Tehrani [3] focus on

the fiber motion process. Both researchers pose a continuum fiber motion model which includes the variations of the radial stiffness and the permeability of the fiber bed during winding. This squeezed sponge model is in contrast to the sequential compaction model posed by Springer to described fiber motion. The key assumption in this sequential compaction model is that consolidation occurs only in the last layer. In [4] Smith and Poursartip have compared these two well established resin flow models and discussed their limitations. Although the squeezed sponge model is the more robust, it requires more extensive materials characterization. In general, the sequential compaction model is a limiting case of the squeezed sponge model. The sequential compaction model is valid (1) if the time scale associated with the winding of each layer is much larger than the time constant of the resin through the fiber bundle; and (2) if the fiber volume fraction is less than 0.60.

In this work, our primary concern is to investigate the effects of winding parameters on composite case quality, where composite case quality refers to the void and fiber volume fractions within the composite. Of particular interest is wet winding of 12 ft diameter graphite reinforced cylinders in which the matrix material is Hercules HBRF-55A resin. The type of resin and size of cylinder are critical in that the resin viscosity, cure kinetics, and winding time determine which flow model is appropriate. The flow model, in turn, determines the pressure gradient within the composite during processing. Once the pressure gradient is known, changes in void size and fiber volume fraction for each layer can be determined.

We have incorporated aspects of both fiber motion models to study this particular, commercially significant, winding case. In addition, the models for the thermochemical, stress strain, and void submodel as originally posed by Springer and coworkers are included. In the following sections, the basic modeling approaches for thermosetting matrix cylinders, as originally formulated by Springer and his coworkers [1], are briefly summarized. Modifications to the original, particularly in the area of fiber motion, are described in detail. Finally, experimental validation for several commercially wound cylinders is presented.

FILAMENT WINDING MODEL

A computer model of the filament winding process was developed which relates the processing conditions to the quality of the composite cylinder (i.e., degree of cure, residual stress state, fiber volume fraction/fiber position, and void size/distribution). The model is comprised of the following submodels. A schematic showing the relationship of the submodels and inputs and outputs is in Figure 2.

THERMOCHEMICAL SUBMODEL

The thermochemical submodel provides the temperature, the viscosity, the degree of cure, and the time required to complete the cure process. A one dimensional energy equation, with temperature varying as a function of radial position and time, is the basis of the thermochemical submodel. The energy absorbed during the cure of the thermosetting matrix is included in the energy balance.

The appropriate one dimensional energy equation is:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (k_r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r}) + \rho_m v_m \dot{Q}_m \quad (1)$$

where t is time, r is the radial coordinate, T is the temperature, ρ is the density, C is the specific heat, and k_r is the thermal conductivity in the radial direction. ρ_m is the density and v_m is the volume fraction of the thermosetting matrix. \dot{Q}_m is the rate at which heat is generated or absorbed by chemical reactions. Because there are no chemical reactions in the fibers, the heat generated term is dependent only on the change in degree of cure of the thermosetting matrix. This rate \dot{Q}_m is related to the degree of cure by the expression

$$\dot{Q}_m = \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) H_u \quad (2)$$

where H_u is the total heat of reaction of the matrix. A relationship for the rate of degree of cure may be found empirically. Once the temperature history is known, the viscosity can be calculated from an expression of the form

$$\mu = f(\alpha, T) \quad (3)$$

Expressions for $d\alpha/dt$, and μ for Hercules HBRF-55A resin can be found in [5].

In order to complete the problem, the initial and boundary conditions must be given. Initially (at time zero) the temperature and degree of cure must be specified at every point inside the composite and the mandrel. For the latter only the temperature is required. As boundary conditions, the temperatures at the composite outside diameter and mandrel inner diameter must be specified.

Solutions to these equations yield the temperature distribution inside the mandrel and inside the composite as a function of time. Degree of cure and matrix viscosity in the composite as a function of time are also determined. This model is the building block for the other submodels. Features not included in the original model developed by Springer [1] include allowing multiple composite materials and hold time between layers.

FIBER MOTION SUBMODEL

The fiber motion submodel yields the fiber position during processing. In filament winding, the fiber position is affected by flow of the resin matrix material, expansion of the mandrel and expansion of the composite. In the fiber motion submodel, only changes in fiber position caused by flow of the matrix are considered. Changes caused by thermal expansion of the mandrel and composite are included in the stress strain submodel.

Two matrix flow submodels have been proposed: the sequential compaction model (scm) [1], and the squeezed sponge model (ssm) [2]. In the literature [3, 4] it has been noted that the scm formulation is limited to cases in which the fiber volume fraction is less than 60% and to "prepreg" winding conditions. Prepreg winding conditions are described as those in which the resin viscosity is high during the winding stage. In [2] a process time constant has been proposed to distinguish between prepreg winding and wet winding. This constant is based on the ratio of the flow time to the wind time for a particular winding operation. The flow time is a measure of the time needed for the flow to complete for one layer.

For the composite cylinders under consideration, the winding time for helical layers is long (9 hours) and the fiber volume fraction is approximately 50%. For the hoop layers, the winding time is much shorter (2 hours) and the fiber volume fraction is approximately 60%. The viscosity of the matrix material, Hercules HBRF-55A, exceeds 2000 $\text{cpa}\cdot\text{s}$ ($\alpha > 0.40$) at room temperature after 9 hours. Under these conditions, the process time constant is on the borderline between prepreg and wet winding. Moreover, the fiber volume fractions are below the limit in which fiber bed stiffness need be included. As such, the sequential compaction model provides the basis of the fiber motion submodel. The original submodel, posed by Lee and Springer, was modified to include conservation of mass and variable fiber bed permeability (as a function of fiber volume fraction).

Each composite layer is idealized as a fiber sheet surrounded by thermoset resin. By treating the fiber sheet as a porous medium, Darcy's law may be employed. The matrix velocity \dot{u}_r through the fiber sheet is given as:

$$\dot{u}_r = -\frac{k}{\mu} \frac{dp}{dr} \quad (4)$$

where k is the apparent permeability of the fiber sheet and dp/dr is the pressure drop across the fiber sheet. The permeability, in turn, is a function of the fiber volume fraction v_f :

$$k = \frac{r_f^2}{4k_z'} \frac{(\frac{\sqrt{v_a}}{\sqrt{v_f}} - 1)^3}{(\frac{v_a}{v_f} + 1)} \quad (5)$$

r_f is the fiber radius, k_z' is the modified Kozeny constant, and v_a is the available fiber volume fraction or packing efficiency at which the transverse flow stops. The stress submodel provides the pressure gradient dp/dr within the cylinder. As each new layer is wound under tension, there is an external radial pressure on the previously wound layers. Consequently a pressure gradient can be determined from elasticity considerations. Because the fiber volume fraction is low, we have assumed that the fiber bed carries none of the pressure load.

Once the resin velocity at the layer interfaces is determined from Eqn (4), the thickness of each ply h is determined from conservation of mass:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho r_f h) = \rho_r r_i (\dot{u}_r)_{in} - \rho_r r_o (\dot{u}_r)_{out} \quad (6)$$

r_f is the current fiber sheet position, $(\dot{u}_r)_{in}$ and $(\dot{u}_r)_{out}$ refer to the resin velocity at the inner r_i and outer r_o radii of a particular layer. The fiber sheet position is updated at each time step to be located midway between the corresponding resin layers. Because the mass of fibers within a fiber sheet remains constant, as the ply thickness changes (with the moving resin) the fiber volume fraction within the ply will change as will the position of the fiber sheet relative to the mandrel. The fiber tension within each layer σ_f is updated to account for the change in fiber position Δu_f :

$$(\sigma_f)_{t+\Delta t} = (\sigma_f)_t + E_f \left(\frac{\Delta u_f}{r_{fo}} \right) \quad (7)$$

where E_f is the fiber modulus and r_{fo} is the initial fiber radial position. Update of the fiber stress is critical. Not only is the fiber stress directly related to the pressure gradient, but as the fiber stress approaches zero fiber buckling will occur within the layer.

STRESS SUBMODEL

The stress submodel results in the stresses and strains in the composite. Stresses and strains are introduced by fiber tension, thermal expansion or contraction, and chemical changes. The effects of fiber tension, temperature and chemical changes may arise simultaneously, however, the stresses and strains are analyzed separately. The sum of the stresses and strains caused by each of these factors is the actual stress and strain in the composite.

The temperature, fiber tension, stresses and strains vary only in the radial directions. An elasticity solution is employed to calculate the six components of the stresses and strains. The solution procedure follows the established techniques of elasticity solutions. A displacement field is assumed which satisfies the equilibrium equations and the compatibility conditions. The latter requires that at each interface the displacements and the normal stresses in adjacent layers be the same. For details of the calculations the reader is referred to [1].

Of particular interest in the current winding model formulation is the implementation of mandrel removal. When the mandrel is removed, there is no radial stress σ_{rr} at the cylinder inner diameter

$$\sigma_{rr} = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad r = r_m \quad (8)$$

This requirement is imposed by adding a radial stress at the cylinder inner diameter that is equal but opposite in magnitude to the contact stress between the mandrel and cylinder. The contact stress corresponds to the radial pressure at the interface at the time the mandrel is removed.

VOID SUBMODEL

Voids are introduced in wet winding during both impregnation and tow placement. In addition to these mechanical means, voids may also be introduced by homogeneous or heterogeneous nucleation. In the void submodel, initiation of voids is not considered, only changes in void size are modeled. The voids are assumed to be spherical and contain a vapor of known composition (i.e. initial concentration of air and water). Void location within the composite cylinder is also assumed to be known. During manufacture, the volume (size) of the void changes because (1) vapor is transported into and out of the void across the void-composite interface, and (2) the pressure changes at the location of the void.

For a spherical void of diameter d , the surface tension Γ at the void composite interface is a function of the pressure inside the void P_v and the pressure surrounding the void P :

$$\Gamma = \frac{d(P_v - P)}{4} \quad (9)$$

The surface tension is found from an empirical relationship [6] and is a function of temperature

(determined in the thermochemical submodel). The surrounding pressure is determined in the resin flow submodels. The pressure within the void is determined by the partial pressures of the water vapor and air within the void. The mass of water vapor within the void changes during processing and can be described by Fickian diffusion across the void/composite interface [6].

Once the mass of vapor inside the void and the pressure at the location are known, the change in void size can readily be calculated from Eqn (9). Changes in void size are halted once the resin has reached gelation. For Hercules HBRF-55A, gelation was set at degree of cure $\alpha = 0.6$.

MODEL VALIDATION AND DISCUSSION

Model predictions for temperature, strain, void behavior, and fiber volume fraction were compared with experimental data. Four 0.51 m (20 in) diameter, thick cylinders were wound by Alliant Technology Systems (Hercules Aerospace Company). Tow tension, layup, and resin viscosity characteristics were varied. Although the actual cylinders wound were 0.51 m diameter, the fiber tension and hold time between layers were adjusted to reflect processing conditions for 3.66 m diameter cylinders. Data obtained from these four cylinders included: temperature during cure as a function of time, strain during cure as a function of time, final cylinder thickness and inside diameter, final void and fiber volume fractions as a function of cylinder radius, and split ring spring back. A brief comparison and discussion of model predictions and data for cylinders 2 and 3 follows. Cylinders 2 and 3 were selected as representative examples of typical results. Abbreviated input data for the model are shown in Table 1.

As shown in Figures 3 and 4, there is good agreement between model predictions and data for temperature and strain. A comparison of model predictions for temperature during cure at an interior hoop layer of cylinder 3 is shown in Figure 3. In Figure 4, experimental hoop strain data during cure of cylinder 2 are compared with model predictions. Several strain gages were mounted at the mandrel outside diameter (at 0, 90, 180 and 270 °). An average hoop strain is reported in Figure 4. The good agreement between model predictions and experimental data indicates that the temperature and strain submodels are functioning properly.

As described previously, the void submodel predicts changes in a "predefined" void during processing. In particular, a spherical void of a particular diameter is placed at a particular location within the composite cylinder. The model provides changes in the diameter of the void during winding and cure. To compare model predictions of void diameter changes with void volume fraction data, only trends in void distribution and differences between void volume fraction can be compared.

The computer model was run with an initial spherical void of 0.001 in diameter inserted at each layer. This initial size is consistent with earlier work by Lee and Springer[1]. Changes in void diameter after winding and after cure for cylinder 2 are shown in Figure 5. As shown in the figure, the following holds true: (1) void diameter is reduced from its initial size, regardless of layer position, (2) void diameter is smallest at the innermost layer (layer 1), and (3) void size does not change after winding. Although the model predictions are for a single void, one can make the argument that these trends could be repeated for various void sizes. That is, in each layer there are a number of voids of various sizes. These voids may be characterized statistically by a mean void size and standard deviation. So as a means of comparing to void volume fraction data, one might expect that void volume fraction will be greatest at the outermost cylinder layers. The graphs of void volume fraction data shown in Figure 6 indicate these trends.

Fiber volume fraction data and model predictions for cylinder 2 are shown in Figure 7. The graph shows the initial fiber volume fraction input to the model, the final fiber volume fraction predicted by the model and the final volume fraction data. The initial volume fraction is also that which Hercules measured prior to winding a particular layer. The initial volume fraction is much greater than the final volume fraction measured in the completed cylinders. The data itself, then, is contradictory. It appears that the resin volume has increased (since the fiber volume must remain constant); mass is not conserved. However, there are two additional possibilities, either: (1) the void volume fraction v_v upon completion is so great as to effectively reduce the fiber volume fraction; or (2) the initial fiber volume fraction data is incorrect. The void data for cylinder 2 (Figure 6) reflect an increase in v_v at the outermost layers. It is interesting to note that the model consistently predicts an increase in fiber volume fraction for each layer. Although mass conservation is imposed, the resin matrix bleeds through the laminate (as occurs with autoclave curing) because the tows are wound under tension. The model predicts a resin rich layer at the cylinder outer diameter. This phenomena is observed during winding; large

quantities of excess resin drop to the work area floor. It has also been observed that the viscosity of the resin that bleeds through is much greater than the viscosity of the layer that has just been wound. This indicates that resin from previously wound layers is flowing through the fiber bed. Finally, the current model, although accounting for changes in void size, does not include void initiation. In calculating changes in fiber volume fraction, it is assumed that the void volume fraction is zero.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The computer model represents the first step in relating winding process variables to final part quality. A particular benefit of the model is that it is founded on first principles. As such, changes in resin systems and materials can easily be incorporated. Model validation indicates that temperature and strain predictions are accurate. Additional work not reported herein includes an update of the fiber motion submodel. In particular, a viscosity mixing model has been added. Additional testing is underway which will focus on precise measurement of the initial fiber and void volume fractions.

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Table 1 Input data for the filament winding model for cylinders 2 and 3.

	cylinder 2	cylinder 3
inner diameter (m)	0.51	0.51
matrix material	HBRF-55A, W sizing	HBRF-55A, W sizing
fiber type	IM7	IM7
layup	inner dia. biased hoop	dispersed hoop
ϕ_o helical	± 22.5	± 22.5
total plies	58	54
tow tension (kg/band)	6.6	helical: 16.4 hoop: 32.8
wind/hold time (hr)	helical: 1/8 hoop: 1.4/2	helical: 1/8 hoop: 1.4/2
cure temperature (C)	177	177

Figure 1. Illustration of the filament winding process.

Figure 2. Schematic showing the relationship among TS WIND submodels, inputs and outputs.

Figure 3. Comparison of model predictions and data for temperature at an interior hoop layer of cylinder 3 (8th hoop layer from the inside cylinder diameter) during cure.

Figure 4. Experimental hoop strain data during cure of cylinder 2 are compared with model predictions. Average hoop strain data for four strain gauges mounted at 0, 90, 180 and 270° on the mandrel outside diameter are reported.

Figure 5. Changes in void diameter after winding and after cure are shown for cylinder 2. An initial void diameter of 0.001 in is placed in each composite layer.

Figure 6. Final void volume fraction layer data for cylinder 2.

Figure 7. Fiber volume fraction v_f data and model predictions are shown for cylinder 2. Initial v_f is the same for the model and the data and is represented by the solid line.